

DESIGN ANALYSIS OF STRUCTURAL STEEL LEAF SPRING AND GLASS FIBER LEAF SPRING

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Abstract

Leaf spring used for vehicle to support the entire weight of vehicle, to provide passenger comfort by absorbing shocks and vibrations, to control axle damping. But steel leaf spring having higher weight (Up to 10–20% of the overall unsprung weight of the vehicle) and major Challenge is to reduce the weight of leaf spring by maintaining its properties. Hence composite material used instead of steel leaf spring as it is light in weight, its extensive properties like high strength, high stiffness, corrosion resistance, low density, high fracture and good toughness. Design analysis done for conventional steel leaf spring, composite E glass and Glass fiber leaf spring to calculate and compare the static properties through ANSYS software.

Keywords: Boundary conditions, Composite leaf spring, Glass fiber leaf spring, Steel leaf spring.

1. Introduction

A significant challenge facing the automotive sector is the reduction of weight. This weight decrease can primarily be accomplished through the use of superior materials, optimized designs, and enhanced manufacturing techniques. The automotive industry has increasingly turned its attention to replacing conventional steel leaf springs with composite leaf springs, thanks to their impressive strength-to-weight ratio and greater strain energy capacity. Research on CFRP materials has enabled the achievement of lighter springs without compromising their load-bearing abilities. The selection of materials hinges on both cost and strength considerations. The aim of this research is to conduct design analysis and fabricate a CFRP leaf spring for lightweight vehicles, ensuring it possesses minimal weight while effectively supporting specific static external forces without failure. In contemporary times, the automobile industry is notably focused on substituting conventional steel leaf springs with composite materials due to their superior strength-to-weight and corrosion resistance ratios. This project encompasses the design, analysis, and development of composite material leaf springs specifically for military jeeps. The material employed in this study is Glass epoxy 28. Our primary aim is to swap out steel to achieve a reduction in the leaf spring's weight. Stiffness emerges as the key design constraint. The selected material is Glass fiber reinforced polymer, commonly referred to as E-glass/epoxy,

which serves as an alternative to steel. Comparative studies on strength, weight, and longevity have been conducted for these two materials. The findings clearly indicate that utilizing composite materials can reduce weight by 85% compared to steel. CATIA V5R20 and CATIA V5 software were utilized for the modeling and analysis of the proposed leaf spring.

1.1 Composite Materials as a Alternative to Steel Leaf Springs

Following are the different types of composite materials used for manufacturing of leaf spring.

1.1.1 Synthetic Fiber-Based Reinforced Composites

A variety of synthetic fibers, such as Glass, graphite, glass, and Kevlar, paired with appropriate resins, are predominantly employed as composite materials because of their outstanding properties like a remarkable strength-to-weight ratio and notable modulus relative to density. A comparative evaluation between steel and composite leaf springs has been performed, considering strength, mass, and cost. A composite reinforced with glass fiber, having diverse thicknesses and widths, was conceived and fabricated using a straightforward hand lay-up method.

1.1.2 Natural Fiber-Based Reinforced Composites

Considering cost-effectiveness and resource sustainability in the modern environment, numerous researchers have aimed to substitute synthetic fibers with natural counterparts for superior results. These materials are biodegradable, sustainable, recyclable, environmentally friendly, and generally less expensive than their synthetic counterparts. Various natural fibers, including jute, sisal, flax, coir, and bamboo, are utilized in automotive, sporting, and structural applications. The ratios of epoxy, E-glass, and silk are crucial in the design, evaluation, and construction of natural fiber-reinforced composites.

1.1.3 Hybrid (Synthetic/Natural) Composites

Design and construction of a hybrid composite (ideally reinforced with glass/Glass) leaf spring for vehicles, which exhibited a sufficiently high natural frequency to avert resonance, were accomplished. The natural frequencies of mono steel leaf springs and hybrid composites were collected. In this configuration, Glass fibers are placed in the outer layers to bolster load-bearing performance, while glass fibers are arranged in the inner layers to enhance damping. An analysis performed using ANSYS revealed that the hybrid laminate can withstand maximum loads while producing lower stresses.

1.2 Material selection:

For conventional materials, SUP9 chosen which standard material is with their properties detailed in below table.

Table 1: Properties of Conventional Material

Properties of SUP9	Value
Young's Modulus (Mpa)	2.1E+5
Tensile Strength (N/mm ²)	1962
Poisson Ratio	0.27
Density (kg/mm ³)	7850

Glass fibers material selected as a composite material due to their improved strength and their properties detailed in below table.

Table 2: Properties of Glass fiber

Properties of Glass fiber	Value
Young's modulus (GPa)	72.3
Tensile strength (GPa)	3.445
Poisson's ratio	0.2
Density (g/cm ³)	2.58

Table 1.4 Comparison of Strength/weight ratio

Glass Fibre	2457 kN.m/kg
Glass Fibre	1307 kN.m/kg
Spider Silk	1069 kN.m/kg
Glass Epoxy Composite	785 kN.m/kg
Balsa axial load	521 kN.m/kg
Steel alloy	254 kN.m/kg
Aluminium alloy	222 kN.m/kg
Polypropylene	89 kN.m/kg
Nylon	69 kN.m/kg

Table 1.5 Comparison of Tensile strength between various materials

Glass steel 1090	3600
High density polyethylene (HDPE)	37
High density polyethylene	37
Stainless steel AISI 302	860
Aluminium alloy 2014-T6	483
E-Glass alone	3450
Glass fiber alone	4127
Glass fiber in a laminate	1600
Kevlar	2757

1.3 Classification of Glass Fiber and Physical Properties

2. Problem Statement

Currently, various segments of the automotive sector are grappling with the substantial task of reducing vehicle weight while ensuring the conservation of natural resources and the efficient use of energy. To achieve this objective, they are focusing on replacing existing materials with innovative, cutting-edge, and lightweight substitutes. In the contemporary landscape, there is a rising need for composite materials. These materials possess multiple essential applications alongside their outstanding characteristics, including high strength, rigidity, excellent wear and corrosion resistance, low density, and remarkable fracture toughness. Since the suspension system constitutes (10–20%) of a vehicle's unsprung mass, it requires a transition to a more lightweight solution.

3. Objective

Design and analysis of E Glass leaf spring for light motor vehicle.

The purpose of this study is to compare the static properties of conventional steel leaf spring with E Glass composite leaf spring.

4. Design calculation

Study focusing on light motor vehicles, we will analyze the Maruti Suzuki Alto 800 vehicle having approximately weight of 850 Kg.

Vehicle Weight = 850 Kg

Pay Load Capacity = 535 Kg

Aggregate Weight = 850 + 535 = 1385 Kg

Aggregate Weight = $W = 1385 \times 10 = 13850\text{N}$

Vehicle having four-wheels, one leaf spring allocated to one wheel manages a 1/4th of the total weight.

Force = $13850/4 = 3462.5\text{ N}$

4.1 CAD

Computer-aided design (CAD) software used for creating, altering, scrutinizing, or refining a design. The objective of CAD software is to enhance the designer's efficiency, improve design quality, streamline communication through documentation, and build a manufacturing database. The outcomes of CAD typically consist of electronic files employed for printing, machining, or various manufacturing operations. The term CADD (Computer Aided Design and Drafting) is also utilized. Its application in the creation of electronic systems is known as electronic design automation (EDA). Within the field of mechanical design, it is called mechanical design automation (MDA) or computer-aided drafting (CAD), which includes the procedure of generating a technical drawing using computer software.

Figure 1: CATIA of Steel Mono-Leaf Spring

4.2 Finite Element Analysis

4.2.1 Synopsis of Finite Element Analysis

Finite element analysis (FEA) is a strategic approach for tackling real-world challenges encountered in engineering fields. Initially, these challenges are reformulated into matrix and partial differential equation forms. Ultimately, these equations are solved to obtain a resolution for the initial problem. The significant quantity of equations involved usually makes manual resolution impractical, highlighting the need for various FEA software tools. A plethora of FEA applications are available for different uses, with Pro Mechanical, ANSYS, NASTRAN, and Gambit being among the most esteemed options.

In numerical mathematics, finite element analysis (FEA) is acknowledged as a computational technique aimed at discovering approximate solutions to boundary value problems linked with partial differential equations. This method entails dividing the extensive problem domain into smaller, manageable units known as finite elements, employing variational techniques from the calculus of variations to tackle the issue by minimizing a corresponding error function. Similar to the idea of approximating a larger circle by connecting numerous small straight lines, FEA utilizes techniques for intertwining several fundamental equations over diminutive sub-regions, referred to as finite elements, to closely mimic a more complex equation across a larger area. Finite element analysis (FEA) is an essential and powerful tool for assessing stresses and strains in structures or components that are too intricate for traditional analytical approaches. This process breaks down the structure or component into multiple tiny segments (a finite number of elements) of various designs, dimensions, and configurations. It is presumed that the elements follow a simplified deformation pattern (linear, quadratic, etc.) and are linked at “nodes,” typically located at corners or edges of the elements. These elements are then combined mathematically using basic principles of structural mechanics, such as force equilibrium and displacement continuity, resulting in a substantial system of simultaneous equations. By harnessing computer resources to solve these extensive simultaneous equations, the deformed shape of the structure or component under applied loads is obtained. Subsequently, stresses and strains are calculated. Finite element analysis (FEA) is arguably the most versatile method for evaluating stress intensity factors. This technique primarily consists of calculating displacements at nodal points of the body, which has been represented as a network of elements interconnected at these nodal locations.

4.2.2 Phases of Finite Element Analysis

The implementation of FEA for engineering problems, like determining deflections and stresses in a structure, requires three fundamental stages:

Phase1: Pre-processing

Phase2: Solution

Phase3: Post-processing

A brief overview of each phase follows.

Phase 1: Pre-processing

Utilizing a CAD tool, either provided by the FEA software or through external 3D CAD modeling applications such as Pro-E, Catia, and Solid Edge, the structure is crafted. The completed FEA model consists of multiple elements that together represent the entire structure. These elements not only symbolize segments of the structure but also imitate its mechanical characteristics and behaviour. Areas with intricate geometries (such as curves, notches, and holes) require a larger number of elements for accurate shape representation, whereas regions with simpler geometries can be modeled using a coarser mesh (or fewer elements). The selection of suitable elements necessitates previous experience with FEA, an understanding of the structure’s behavior,

knowledge of the elements available in the software, and their properties. The elements connect at the nodes, or common points. Throughout the pre-processing phase, the geometry of the structure, along with constraints, loads, and mechanical properties, are established. Thus, the entire structure is thoroughly defined through the geometric model during the pre-processing phase. The structure described by nodes and elements is termed a “mesh.”

Phase 2: Solution

In this stage, the geometry, constraints, mechanical properties, and loads are applied to formulate matrix equations for each element, which are subsequently integrated to create a global matrix equation for the structure. The form of both the individual and structural equations is:

$$\{F\} = [K] \{u\} \quad (1)$$

Where

{F} = External force matrix,

[K] = Global stiffness matrix,

{u} = Displacement matrix.

This equation is then solved for deflections. Using the resulting deflection values, strain, stress, and reactions are calculated. All results are recorded and can later be employed to create graphical representations and charts during the post-analysis phase

Phase 3: Post-processing

This completes the final stage of a finite element evaluation. The outcomes obtained in stage 2 generally appear as raw data, which can be difficult to interpret. During the post-analysis phase, a CAD application is used to modify the data for producing the deflected shape of the structure, generating stress visualizations, animations, and more. A graphical representation of the results is extremely beneficial for comprehending the structure's performance.

ANSYS software employs the Finite Element Method (FEM) to address any issue.

4.3 Steps of Finite Element Method (FEM)

In the current study, ANSYS (Analysis System) software is utilized for the analysis. Essentially, it employs the Finite Element Method (FEM) to address any issue. The following are the steps in detail:

Step 1: Geometry

Step 2: Meshing (Discretization)

Step 3: Boundary condition

Step 4: Solve (Solution)

Step 5: Interpretation of Results

Details are as follows

4.3.1 Geometry

The Workbench encompasses various types of analyses, including static, modal, harmonic, explicit dynamics, CFD, ACP tool post, CFX, topology optimization, etc., tailored to the defined problem.

Figure 2: Geometry

Step 1: Requirements for substances like copper, steel, grey cast iron, composite materials, and fluid domain substances are defined in the engineering data. For example, the standard material in ANSYS is structural steel.

Step 2: The design crafted using any CAD application, such as CATIA, PRO E, SOLIDWORKS, INVENTOR, etc., is imported into the geometry section. Should any alterations be necessary, they can be made in the geometry area of Design Modeler or Space Claim.

Step 3: Upon importing the component into the model section, Material is assigned to the component per the existing substance. The connections are inspected in the contact area, like bonded, frictionless, frictional, no separation, etc., for multi-body components. Meshing or discretization occurs to divide components into smaller parts (elements) based on size, with tetrahedral mesh and hexahedral mesh favoured for 3D shapes, while quadrilateral or triangular meshes are typically selected for 2D shapes.

Step 4: Boundary conditions are applied based on the analysis, including fixed support, pressure, force, displacement, and velocity as required.

Step 5: The problem is now distinctly defined, and the solve option is selected to obtain the solution regarding equivalent stress, strain, energy, reaction force, etc.

ANSYS Workbench 21.0 serves as the environment to perform modal analysis on thrust coupling. As the most advanced CAE software, ANSYS Workbench 21.0 provides users with simulation modules across various fields, including structure, fluid, electromagnetic, heat transfer, and more. It remains the industry's pinnacle of engineering simulation technology integration, offering an intuitive and user-friendly interface along with efficient pre-processing and post-processing functions and its extensive solution capabilities

Figure 3: Material Properties of Structural Steel

Properties of Outline Row 3: Structural Steel		
A	B	C
Property	Value	Unit
Material Field Variables	Table	
Density	7850	kg m ⁻³
Isotropic Secant Coefficient of Thermal Expansion		
Isotropic Elasticity		
Derive from	Young's Modu...	
Young's Modulus	2E+11	Pa
Poisson's Ratio	0.3	
Bulk Modulus	1.6667E+11	Pa
Shear Modulus	7.6923E+10	Pa

Properties	
☐ Volume	8.1065e+005 mm ³
☐ Mass	6.3636 kg

4.3.2 Meshing

ANSYS Meshing stands out as a dynamic, smart, and automated high-efficiency resource intended for universal application. It assembles the optimal mesh to guarantee accurate and effective Multiphysics outcomes. With a mere click, a mesh customized for a particular analysis can be generated for every component within a model. For the experienced user aiming to refine the mesh, total command over the generation parameters is offered. The strong capabilities of concurrent processing are utilized automatically to reduce the wait time for mesh generation. Creating the most appropriate mesh is vital for engineering analyses. ANSYS Meshing acknowledges the kinds of solutions relevant to the project and applies the associated criteria to create the best-suited mesh. It integrates effortlessly with each solver in the ANSYS Workbench framework. For rapid evaluations or for novice and occasional users, an effective mesh can be produced with just a single click. ANSYS Meshing selects the most fitting options based on the analysis type and the geometry of the model. Importantly, ANSYS Meshing can take advantage of the available cores on the machine for parallel processing, greatly accelerating mesh creation. Parallel meshing is offered without additional costs or licensing restrictions.

Figure 4: Meshing of Structural Steel Leaf Spring

Statistics	
☐ Nodes	26613
☐ Elements	4464

The conclusive design of the 4-wheeler Steel Leaf Spring comprises 26,613 nodes and 4,464 elements, featuring an element size of 10 mm.

4.3.3 Element Categories

When addressing complex geometries or considerable fluctuations in flow length scales, a triangular/tetrahedral mesh can be generated with significantly fewer cells compared to an equivalent quadrilateral/hexahedral mesh. This benefit stems from the fact that triangular/tetrahedral meshes facilitate cell clustering in particular zones of the flow domain. In contrast, structured quadrilateral/hexahedral meshes often allocate cells in superfluous areas. Unstructured quadrilateral/hexahedral meshes offer many advantages akin to those of triangular/tetrahedral meshes when confronted with geometries of moderate complexity.

- For straightforward shapes, utilize quadrilateral/hexahedral meshes.
- For shapes of moderate intricacy, use unstructured quadrilateral/hexahedral meshes.
- For shapes that are somewhat complex, implement triangular/tetrahedral meshes with prism layers.
- For exceedingly intricate shapes, adopt exclusively triangular/tetrahedral meshes.

4.3.4 Boundary Conditions

A boundary condition for the model includes designating a known value for either displacement or a related load. For any given node, you can set either the load or the displacement, but not both at once. The primary types of loading alternatives available in FEA consist of force, pressure, and temperature. These can be applied to points, surfaces, edges, nodes, and elements, or they can be distanced from certain features. Excessively constrained or insufficiently constrained models can produce stress assessments that are so inaccurate they become useless for engineers. Ideally, we could manage extensive assemblies of components linked by contact elements, but such a task is frequently beyond the financial and resource capabilities of most. Nevertheless, we can optimize the potential of the computing hardware available to us, which requires a thorough understanding of how to implement realistic boundary conditions

Weight of Vehicle = 850 Kg
Maximum Load Carrying Capacity = 535 Kg
Total Weight = 850 + 535 = 1385 Kg
Total Weight = $W = 1385 \times 10 = 13850\text{N}$

4-wheeler vehicle having a single leaf spring and it corresponding to one of the wheels takes up $\frac{1}{4}$ of the total weight.

$$F = 13850/4 = 3462.5\text{ N}$$

Figure 5: Boundary condition of Structural Steel Leaf Spring

4.4 Results

4.4.1 Total Deformation of steel leaf spring

Boundary conditions are applied on steel leaf spring and it is observed that maximum deformation is 1.3766 mm and minimum deformation is 00 mm.

Figure 6: Total Deformation of Structural Steel Leaf Spring

4.4.2 Equivalent Stress of steel leaf spring

Upon the implementation of boundary conditions on the steel leaf spring, it is noted that the maximum and minimum equivalent (von-Mises) stresses produced are 175.04 MPa and 1.167e-6, respectively

Figure 7: Equivalent Stress of Steel Leaf Spring

4.4.3 Maximum equivalent elastic strain of steel leaf spring

Maximum equivalent elastic strain calculated for steel leaf spring is 0.0008755.

Figure 8: Equivalent Elastic Strain of Steel Leaf Spring

4.5 Design analysis of Glass Fiber Composite Leaf Spring

4.5.1 FEA of Glass Fiber Composite Leaf Spring

Figure 9: Geometry of Glass Fiber Leaf Spring

4.5.2 Material properties

Figure 10: Material Properties of Composite Glass Fiber

Properties of Outline Row 4: E-Glass			
	A	B	
1	Property	Value	
2	Density	2600	kg m ⁻³
3	Isotropic Secant Coefficient of Thermal Expansion		
4	Coefficient of Thermal Expansion	5E-06	C ⁻¹
5	Isotropic Elasticity		
6	Derive from	Young's Modulus ...	
7	Young's Modulus	7.3E+10	Pa
8	Poisson's Ratio	0.22	
9	Bulk Modulus	4.3452E+10	Pa
10	Shear Modulus	2.9918E+10	Pa

Properties	
☐ Volume	8.1065e+0...
☐ Mass	2.1077 kg

4.5.3 Meshing

Figure 11: Meshing of Glass Fiber composite Leaf Spring

4.5.4 Boundary condition

Figure 12: Boundary Condition on Glass Fiber composite Leaf Spring

4.5.5 Total deformation

After applying boundary conditions on glass fiber leaf spring it is observed that maximum deformation is 3.7725 mm and minimum deformation is 00 mm.

Figure 13: Total Deformation of Glass fiber composite leaf spring

4.5.6 Equivalent Stress

Upon the implementation of boundary conditions on the E Glass composite leaf spring, it is noted that the maximum and minimum equivalent (von-Mises) stresses produced are 174.6 Mpa and $5.7124e-7$ respectively.

Figure 14: Equivalent Stress of Glass fiber composite leaf spring

4.5.7 Equivalent Elastic Strain

The maximum and minimum equivalent elastic strain observed in glass fiber leaf spring is 0.002406 and $7.825e-12$ respectively.

Figure 15: Equivalent Elastic Strain of Glass fiber composite leaf spring

4.5.8 Comparison of FEA Result:

Table 3: Comparison of FEA results of steel and CFRP leaf spring

Parameter	Steel Leaf Spring	Glass Fibre leaf Spring
Weight (Kg)	6.36	2.107
Total Deformation (mm)	1.376	3.7725
Equivalent Stress (MPa)	175.04	174.6
Equivalent Strain	0.00087555	0.002406

5. Future Scope

The development and static structural assessment of both steel and composite leaf springs have been conducted. A comparison has been established between the composite leaf spring and the steel leaf spring, both featuring identical designs and load-bearing capacities.

Furthermore, the current study employs the hand lay-up method for the fabrication of E Glass composite leaf springs.

In the future, evaluating the fatigue lifespan of the composite leaf spring could facilitate dynamic analysis.

The utilization of composite leaf springs leads to a reduction in vehicle weight, resulting in measurable improvements in the fuel efficiency of light motor vehicles.

Various manufacturing methods may be explored to enhance the production rate of composite leaf springs. Sleek designs of suspension systems can be developed by integrating lightweight composite leaf springs. Composite leaf springs can also be adapted for heavy-duty vehicles by enhancing the properties of composite materials and adjusting design specifications.

6. Conclusion

Comparison has been made between composite leaf spring with steel leaf spring having same design and same load carrying capacity.

The stress and displacements have been calculated using ANSYS for steel leaf spring and composite leaf spring. From the static analysis results it is found that there is a maximum displacement of 1.376 mm in the steel leaf spring and 7.1935 mm in Glass fiber leaf spring.

By analyzing the design, it was found that all the stresses in the leaf spring were well within the allowable limits and with good factor of safety.

The strength to weight ratio is higher for composite leaf spring than conventional steel spring with similar design.

References

- S. Rajesh , G. B. Bhaskar, 2016, “ Performance of leaf springs made of composite material subjected to low frequency impact loading”*Journal of Mechanical Science and Technology* 30 (9) (2016) 4291-4298.
- Jamadar, N.I., Kivade, S.B. & Tati, P., 2018, “Prediction of Residual Fatigue Life of Composite Mono Leaf Spring Based on Stiffness Degradation”*Article in Journal of Failure Analysis and Prevention* 1516–1525 October 2018.
- K.Ashwini, Prof C.V. Mohan Rao, 2018, “Design and Analysis of Leaf Spring using Various Composites – An Overview” *Science Direct Materials Today: Proceedings* 5 (2018) 5716–5721.
- Pankaj Saini, Ashish Goel, Dushyant Kumar, 2013, “design and analysis of composite leaf spring for light vehicles” *International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology* Vol. 2, Issue 5, May 2013.
- Mohammed Asif Kattimani, Mohammed Iqbal Khatib, Aiman Quraishi, Mohammed Ashfaque Inayath, 2019, “Design Analysis and Fabrication of Composite Leaf Spring” *International Journal of Research in Advent Technology*, Vol.7, No.3, March 2019.

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Shad Mohammad Shohel, Shaptarshi Sen Gupta, Sabbir Hossain Riyad, 2022, “Weight optimization and finite element analysis of automobile leaf spring: A design construction referred to electric vehicle” International Conference on Advances in Mechanical Engineering-2022, IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering.

Ravi Ratnakar , Mukesh Kumar Sahu, 2021, “Design and Analysis of Composite Built Leaf Spring Systems For Heavy and Light Vehicle” International Journal of Technology and Emerging Sciences 2021, IJTES | Volume 01|| Issue 03|| October 2021 | Page 12-16.